

Trust. Community.
Empowerment

Trusted Connections reimagines digital inclusion by putting trust, community, and empowerment at the heart of how people access, learn, and thrive in digital life.

2026

Trusted Connections project policy brief

From 5 months of action to sustainable digital inclusion

Over an intensive five month period, the Trusted Connections project demonstrated the powerful impact of community driven, trust based approaches to digital inclusion: training of mentors as trusted parties, establishing local digital hubs, and engaging hundreds of participants across the North East. While the timeframe limited the ability to fully evidence long term sustainability, the project successfully created the foundations for ongoing impact by building local capacity, strengthening community partnerships, and fostering confidence and agency among participants. Its legacy lies in the relationships formed, the mentoring networks established, and a model of inclusion that can continue to grow beyond the life of the project.

Overview

The Trusted Connections project is a community-led digital inclusion initiative addressing persistent digital inequalities in the North East of England. Delivered through a partnership between Durham University, Digital Safety CIC, and a network of grassroots organisations (Let's Connect, Sacriston Youth Project, Auxillia Youth Services, The Newcastle Rugby Foundation, Pact House and BornGood), the project focuses on supporting four priority groups: young people, individuals at risk of or experiencing NEET status, unemployed adults, and adults aged 55 and over. Its central aim is to enhance digital access, skills, confidence, and agency through trusted, community-based approaches.

At its core, the project challenges traditional models of digital inclusion that prioritise short-term skills training. Instead, it adopts a relational approach grounded in a pedagogy of empowerment, recognising that meaningful digital participation depends on trust, social context, and sustained support.

Approach and model

The project is underpinned by a conceptual framework structured around four key pillars of digital inclusion:

1. **Access:** ensuring availability of devices, connectivity, and support
2. **Digital literacies:** developing practical and critical digital skills
3. **Agency and empowerment:** building confidence and the capacity to act
4. **Inclusive participation and support:** fostering community-based learning and engagement.

At its core, the project challenges traditional models of digital inclusion that prioritise short-term skills training. Instead, it adopts a relational approach grounded in a pedagogy of empowerment, recognising that meaningful digital participation depends on trust, social context, and sustained support.

The four pillars of digital inclusion presented above reflect a change from viewing digital inclusion as a technical issue to understanding it as a social and cultural process shaped by lived experience, trust, and local context.

A central innovation of the project is its community-based mentoring model. Mentors are not positioned primarily as technical experts but as “meaningful others”, i.e., trusted individuals embedded within communities who support others in navigating digital environments. This approach emphasises relationship-building, ongoing interaction, and contextual relevance, enabling participants to develop both digital skills and critical awareness over time.

Mentors play a key role as cultural mediators, helping participants interpret digital practices, recognise risks, and engage confidently. Importantly, the model fosters a cycle of learning in which participants may themselves become mentors, creating a sustainable and expanding network of support.

Project delivery

The Trusted Connections project was delivered through a set of interconnected components:

- **Mentor Network:** trusted members of the community as trained mentors providing peer-based support
- **Community Digital Hubs:** local hubs offering safe, accessible learning environments
- **Mobile Pop-Up Lab:** flexible provision reaching diverse communities
- **Online Learning Platform:** hosting training materials and mentoring support
- **Digital Skills Sessions:** delivered across community contexts
- **Festival of Digital Culture and Inclusion:** promoting engagement and sharing best practice

All elements were co-designed with community partners to ensure relevance and responsiveness to local needs.

Over a five-month period, the project achieved or exceeded all key performance indicators:

27 mentors trained; **5** community digital hubs established; **113** digital inclusion sessions delivered; **369** unique participants engaged; **1,380** total session participations recorded. The creation of an **online platform** and the **Festival of Digital Culture and inclusion** was hosted by Durham University and some partners with **10** individual events across the week-long Festival

Key insights and impact

1. Trust is an essential digital infrastructure

The project shows that trust functions as crucial infrastructure. Without it, digital services, platforms, and training remain underused or avoided. Participants engaged because support came from trusted, relatable individuals within familiar community settings. Mentors were perceived as peers rather than experts or officials, reducing anxiety and building confidence.

2. Digital confidence grows through relationships, not one-off training

Participants reported significant improvements in:

- Confidence using devices and platforms
- Understanding of online safety, scams, and privacy
- Awareness of digital footprints and employability implications
- Emotional wellbeing and balanced digital habits

The strength of these outcomes was strongly influenced by the sustained and relational support offered.

3. Community mentoring creates lasting capacity

The mentoring model generated benefits beyond the life of individual sessions:

- Mentors gained qualifications, skills, and increased confidence in their skills and ability
- Community organisations strengthened their role as trusted digital hubs
- Learning spread informally across families and generations
- Digital knowledge became embedded locally rather than externally delivered

This creates a multiplier effect, where digital inclusion becomes more self-supported and therefore sustainable.

4. Place-based approaches reduce exclusion more effectively

Delivery grounded in existing community spaces enabled engagement with groups often labelled as “hard to reach”. The evidence suggests these groups are better understood as historically underserved and require approaches that fit local practices, needs, and priorities.

Strengths of the approach

- Relational model: builds trust and sustained engagement
- Community-embedded delivery: ensures relevance and accessibility
- Flexible curriculum: adaptable to diverse needs and contexts
- Co-production: involves communities in design and delivery
- Scalability: provides a transferable model for wider adoption

Limitations and learning

The primary limitation of the project relates to its short timeframe, which constrained opportunities for:

- deeper relationship-building
- extended mentor development
- long-term impact evaluation

Participants and partners highlighted the value of longer-term engagement to strengthen trust and embed learning.

The evaluation is also largely based on self-reported outcomes, with limited opportunity for longitudinal assessment of sustained change.

A scalable blueprint for action

The Trusted Connections project offers a transferable blueprint for digital inclusion policy, one that is:

- Relational, rather than deficit-based: focuses on strengths, lived experience, and community knowledge
- Trust led: mentors and organisations rooted in place
- Flexible: learning unites with adaptable resources rather than fixed curricula
- Sustainable: recognises that confidence and agency develop over time and support is ongoing
- Cross sector: linking higher education, community organisations, and social enterprises

This approach reframes digital inclusion as a shared civic responsibility, not an individual burden.

The Trusted Connections project demonstrates that digital inclusion is most effective when rooted in trust, relationships, and community ownership. This model offers a scalable, evidence-based framework for addressing digital exclusion across diverse contexts.

Recommendations

1. Embed trust-based approaches in digital inclusion policy

Policymakers should recognise trust as foundational infrastructure for digital engagement. Funding models should support relational, long-term approaches rather than short-term technical training alone.

2. Invest in community mentor networks

Sustained investment in recruiting, training, and supporting community mentors creates lasting local capacity. Mentors should be drawn from the communities they serve to ensure cultural relevance and relatability.

3. Support place-based, co-designed delivery

Digital inclusion programmes should be designed with communities, not for them. Delivery through trusted local spaces increases reach and engagement with underserved groups.

4. Recognise digital inclusion as a social process

Moving beyond skills-deficit models requires acknowledging that digital confidence grows through relationships, context, and ongoing support rather than isolated interventions.

5. Scale the model through partnerships

The Trusted Connections framework is transferable. Strategic partnerships with local authorities, housing associations, health services, and voluntary organisations can extend reach while maintaining community ownership.

Conclusion

The Trusted Connections project provides a compelling model for addressing digital exclusion through community-driven, relational approaches. By foregrounding trust, local knowledge, and sustained support, it moves beyond traditional skills-based interventions and positions digital inclusion as a shared social process.

Its success demonstrates that meaningful digital engagement depends not only on what people know, but on who they can learn with and trust. As such, the project offers valuable insights for policymakers, practitioners, and organisations seeking to build inclusive and sustainable digital futures.

About this report

This report has been authored by Dr Cristina Costa and Dr Michaela Oliver, Durham University, UK.

The Trusted Connections project was funded by UK Government's Department for Science, Innovation and Technology Digital Inclusion Innovation Fund. Its contents are the sole responsibility of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of DSIT.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the project partners: Digital Safety CIC, Born Good, Let's Connect, Sacriston Youth Project, Auxillia Youth Services, Pact House and the Newcastle Rugby Foundation, collaborators, and mentors for their work and support during the project, as well as those who participated in the project sessions.

Please cite this report as:

Costa, C. and Oliver, M. (2026). Trusted Connections Project: Policy Brief, Durham University.
